

A Study of North Maharashtra University Library:

Dr. Jyoti Magar

Pramiladevi Patil Art's and Science College Neknoor Dist Beed

ABSTRACT

As a measure of decentralization and reorganization of the university education in the State of Maharashtra, this University has been established and incorporated by Government of Maharashtra state Act XXIX of 1989, with a view to meet the educational needs of students as well as teachers of the University. It was a felt need of this University to initiate Library and Information Services to support academic activities of the University. For this purpose, the Central Library was established during 1991-1992.

Keywords: Research Methodology, Definition, library total information :

INTRODUCTION

Hypothesis:

- Reviewing the relevant library
- Practitioner study of material collection available in library
- Viewing material information available online

Research Methodology: case study :

Definition:

A case study is a detailed study of a specific subject, such as a person, group, place, event, organization, or phenomenon. Case studies are commonly used in social, educational, clinical, and business. (<https://www.scribbr.com>)

A case study research design usually involves qualitative methods, but quantitative methods are sometimes also used. Case studies are good for describing, comparing, evaluating and understanding different aspects of a research problem.

Subject Categories available journal:

Agricultural and Biological Sciences
Arts and Humanities Biochemistry, Genetics and,
Molecular Biology

Business, Management and Accounting
Chemical Engineering
Chemistry
Computer Science
Decision Sciences
Dentistry
Earth and Planetary Sciences
Economics, Econometrics and Finance
Energy, Engineering
Environmental Science
Health Professions
Immunology and Microbiology
Materials Science
Mathematics, Medicine
Neuroscience, Nursing
Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics
Physics and Astronomy
Psychology
Social Sciences
Veterinary
Multidisciplinary
Library Collection

Sr. No.	Library	Books	Text Books	Back Volumes	Theses	Total
1.	Knowledge Resource Center	88790	3000	6817	6489	105096
2.	University Departmental Libraries	17000	-	-	-	17000
3.	Pratap Philosophy Centre, Amalner	6240	-	-	-	6240
4.	Eklavya Training Centre, Nandurbar	2224	-	-	-	2224

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

5.	Mahatma Gandhi Tatvadnyan Centre, Dhule	4000	-	-	-	4000
6.	Mahatma Gandhi Adhyan & Research Centre, NMU. Jalgaon	1756	-	-	-	1756
Total Books						136316

(<http://14.139.120.185/>)

E-Journals

Licensed Open Access

Chemical Society (37 Journals)

American Institute of Physics (18 Journals)

American Physical Society (10 Journals)

Economic and Political weekly

Annual Reviews (33 Journals)

Institute of Physics (46 Journals)

Cambridge University Press (224 Journals)

Emerald (LIS Collection) (29 Journals)

J-STOR (1401+ Journals)

(<http://nptel.iitm.ac.in>)

Other Material

CDs / DVDs	Manuscripts
950	15

Current Journals

Journals	Total No.
Journals subscribed	142
Received Gratis	10

E-Journals

UGC- Infonet	Web of Science	JNISCAIR	IAS
5000+	12000 Journals	20	10

Research Project Progress Reports

Sr. No.	Project Title	Investigator	View Project Report
1.	Clean synthesis and bioactivity evaluation of newer benzimidazole compounds (F. No. 41-302/2012, 13/07/12)	Prof. P. P. Mahulikar	View
2.	A Study on Taste Masking of some Bitter Drugs (File No. 43-159/2014 (SR))	Prof. J. B. Naik	View
3.	Deposition and Electrical Characterization of Rare Earth Oxide Doped High-k Thin Films on Si Substrates for Nanoscale MOSFETs	Prof. A. M. Mahajan	View
4.	Design Modelling and simulation of stirred ball mill and ultrasound assisted dispersion of nanopigments for utilization in formulations of coatings, printing ink, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetics (F. No. 40-11/2011(SR))	Mr. Tushar D. Deshpande	View
5.	Synthesis, Docking Studies and Antituberculosis Evaluation of Some Newer Promising Heterocycles Derived from Isoniazid and Ethyl 2-cyano-3, 3-Bis(methylthio) acrylate	Dr. Dipak S. Dalal	View

(https://nmu.ac.in/knowledge_resource)_

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student have to submit an application form and provide soft copy of the thesis. The facility is made available through official email ID of KRC (library@nmu.ac.in)

The Steps are as follows:

The Drillbit-Extreme access is also provided to research supervisors for checking research papers of their students.

- Students send thesis soft copy to library@nmu.ac.in at the time of final submission after pre-viva.
- KRC Official will forward the soft copy to the Drillbit-Extreme service. The process may take 1-2 working days.
- KRC Official will forward the analysis link to the student along with plagiarism checking application, format for cd/dvd naming conventions and instructions to download plagiarism certificate.
- Students can follow the instructions and download plagiarism check certificate from the analysis link and attach the same in the thesis hard copy.

Library provides following services

- Access to online journals under UGC-INFLIBNET program
- Home Lending Services
- Reprography
- Readingroom facilities availability
- Internet Searching
- Reference Services
- Inter Library Loan Services
- Current Awareness Services
- Online Public Access Catalog

Best Practices:

- Best User Award for Students
- Extra-curricular
- Books Exhibition

Membership:

- For University Department Teaching Staff.
- Non-Teaching Staff of University and University Departments.
- Students, Teaching Departments.
- Researchers.

Library Rules:

Who can become the member?

All Post Graduate Students admitted in University departments, and all the faculties, Scientists and Academicians of the University.

Post-Graduate students and teachers of affiliated colleges for reference only. All faculty members of the University Departments. University authorities. All M. Phil. & Ph.D. Students/Research Associates and Temporary faculty of the University campus are eligible for membership.

CONCLUSION:

Various aspects have been reviewed in the said study, the overall background of the library, information about the online literature of the books available in the library, which research method has been used to carry out the said research work, what are the objectives of the said research etc. have been studied in the said research paper

REFERENCE

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